

A D-band Transmitter Achieving 57.6 Gb/s and 30 dBm EIRP Based on Channel Aggregation 45-nm ICs and a Low-Profile Flat Lens Antenna

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Abstract—We present two high-efficiency baseband-to-D-band transmitting systems based on a novel channel-aggregation architecture. They comprise a first integrated circuit for channel aggregation at intermediate frequency, a two-channel 45-nm CMOS transmitter flip-chipped on antenna-in-package which illuminates a high-gain flat lens antenna in standard printed circuit board technology. The two signals emitted by the active antenna module, in adjacent bands, are aggregated over the air and collimated by the flat lens. Two transmitters using, respectively, a standard and a folded transmitarray antenna, three times thinner than the former one, are realized and compared. They achieve similar performance in the operating band (139.3-156.6 GHz), with a measured peak effective isotropic radiated power of 30 dBm. A wireless point-to-point link is demonstrated with the proposed transmitting system and a commercial receiver. A data rate of 57.6 Gb/s is measured at 1 m using 8 channels and a 16-QAM scheme, with an energy efficiency of 27.4 pJ/b.

Index Terms— D-band, CMOS 45nm, millimeter-wave antennas, antennas-in-package, active antennas, lens antennas.

I. INTRODUCTION

WIRELESS transmitters for high-data-rate links are key building blocks for the next-generation communication networks [1]-[5]. Most of them target the sub-THz spectrum, due to the wide available bandwidth (BW). However, these architectures have to face challenging trade-offs among power consumption, BW, and transmitted power, due to the high path loss and the feasible modulation schemes for large-band channels, which are usually limited to 4 to 6 bits/s/Hz.

This work presents a D-band transmitting system comprising a wideband channel-aggregation transmitter (TX) chipset and a compact high-gain antenna, and demonstrates a complete wireless link. A channel-aggregation architecture [1] is selected for the up-converter from baseband (BB) to D-band, which allows one to optimize the signal fractional BW at each frequency conversion stage, without limiting the total BW of the emitted signal. With this approach, the power consumption of all sub-systems, including the digital interfaces, can be reduced [6]. The proposed D-band module covers a band of 17.3 GHz by up-converting 8 baseband adjacent channels, each

covering a range of 2.16 GHz. It comprises two different 45-nm CMOS integrated circuits (ICs). The first one performs a four-channel up-conversion and a channel aggregation from I/Q BB to an intermediate frequency (IF) band, centered at 61.56 GHz. The second IC is a two-channel transmitter, similar to that in [6]. The channel aggregation at IF is achieved on-chip using a passive hybrid 4-way power combiner, whereas the two output signals of the TX IC at D-band are combined over the air, using a high-gain transmitarray antenna (TA). The planar lens is illuminated by two printed antennas, each fed by one of the two output signals of the TX IC, realized in the low-cost printed-circuit board (PCB) where the TX IC is flip-chipped. Two different TX systems based on a standard and a folded TA architecture [7], respectively, are prototyped and characterized. They are designed using the same flat lens and two slightly modified versions of the active antenna-in-package (AiP) which comprises the TX IC and the two antenna feeds. The distance between the AiP and the planar lens in the folded TA system is a third of that used in the conventional TA system. The performance of the two systems, e.g. radiation patterns and effective isotropic radiated power (EIRP), are compared. Both antenna systems enable a data rate (DR) of 57.6 Gb/s over a 1-m wireless point-to-point link, using a 16 QAM with 1.8 Gbaud per baseband channel. They attain a peak EIRP of 30 dBm, thanks to the TA which achieve an average realized gain of about 25 dBi. The energy consumption of the TX module is only 27.4 pJ/b. The link is characterized using a commercial receiver (RX) in a hardware-in-the-loop system-level validation platform. The link range is greatly enhanced with respect to state-of-the-art D-band modules based on low-gain antennas [3], without resorting to energy-hungry phased array systems [4], [5]. Moreover, the proposed over-the-air channel aggregation significantly improves the efficiency and radiated power with respect to architectures using lossy guided combiners. The active folded TA system achieves the same BW and an average EIRP about 10 dBm higher than that reported in our previous work [9] for a TA-based TX module using a diplexer for channel aggregation. Moreover, the height of the folded TA module (~9.2 mm) is reduced by a factor 3.5 with respect to the system in [9].

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This article is an extended version of our conference paper [7] and reports some results presented in [8]. Compared to these works, a more extensive analysis of the link budget and an in-depth description of the antenna system with new numerical and experimental data, e.g. the EIRP of the stand-alone antenna feeds and an estimation of the antenna gain, are presented. New details on packaging and assembly are presented. More information on system requirements such as phase noise and jitter is provided. Moreover, the digital baseband processing used for the link demonstration is discussed for the first time. Finally, a wireless link with a 1-m range and equal performance compared to the 42-cm link presented in [8] is demonstrated using TAs at both the TX and RX ends.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the TX architecture and the link budget. Section III describes the ICs performing the two up-conversion and IF channel-aggregation stages. Section IV presents the antenna design. Section V reports the experimental characterization of the two developed active TA systems, in terms of radiation patterns and EIRP. Section VI describes the experiments and figures of merit of several point-to-point links using the TX and a commercial RX. The signal processing and RF impairments compensation algorithms used in the digital baseband RX are discussed. Finally, Section VII compares the performance of the proposed TX with the state of the art and draws the main conclusions.

II. TRANSMITTER ARCHITECTURE AND LINK BUDGET

The D-band (110-170 GHz) may offer throughputs that are competitive with optical fiber communications. It can be used to reach a data-rate of at least 100 Gb/s at distances up to a few hundreds of meters. These are common requirements of fronthaul and backhaul links for 5G and beyond-5G networks [10], [11]. Other applications include short-distance links for kiosk or docks for fast downloading, medium-distance links to replace cables in data centers, and guided links using dielectric waveguides [12]. In this context, maximizing the spectral and the energy efficiencies are key objectives. The maximum data-rate that can be achieved by a wireless link is ultimately limited by the available BW and the noise according to Shannon capacity theorem [13]. Figure 1 shows the maximum attainable data-rate for a set of reasonable links parameters shown in the figure inset. A fractional BW of 20 % is considered for all carrier frequencies. The figure compares the maximum capacity of the channel for different modulation schemes. Interestingly, the peak capacity is achieved for 16 QAM, at different distances and carrier frequencies. It is worth noting that a 100 Gb/s rate can be achieved at 200 m using a 16 QAM. Thus, a BW of a few tens of GHz is required, at D-band, to reach a 100 Gb/s data-rate. This distance range requires a high transmitted power and low-noise receiver. Short-distance links can also attain 100 Gb/s data-rate with much lower TX power and higher receiver noise figure (see Fig. 1b). Even in this case, the maximum capacity is obtained using 16 QAM. In this work, channel-aggregation architectures are proposed as an energy efficient alternative to conventional broadband single-channel transceivers. They support RF BWs of tens of GHz, but require much smaller baseband BWs compared to conventional architectures.

Fig. 1. Maximum link data-rate as a function of carrier frequency, according to Shannon capacity limit, for a 20% fractional BW channel for two different scenarios: (a) TX with high output power and low noise figure RX; (b) lower output power TX and higher noise figure RX.

Fig. 2. Example of a possible channel aggregation TX architecture.

A. Channel Aggregation Architecture

The basic idea behind the proposed architecture consists in building the wideband signal to be radiated by combining multiple narrower band channels. The general principle and a

possible architecture are illustrated in Fig. 2, where a total RF BW of 34.56 GHz is obtained by combining 16 channels of 2.16 GHz each. This BW is the standard channel BW at 60 GHz which is selected as the IF band for our architecture. The choice of the BW responds also to a tradeoff between the need of reducing it, to optimize the power consumption and to relax analog and RF circuit constraints, and the need of minimizing the number of channels required to achieve an overall 100 Gb/s data rate with 16-QAM. Fig. 2 shows the TX section. Instead of bringing the 16 channels directly from BB to RF band, a two-step up-conversion scheme is preferred. This design reduces the number of required local oscillator (LO) signals. Indeed, by grouping the BB channels in bundles of four channels and implementing a first up-conversion to IF, only four LOs are required, assuming that all bundles of four BB channels share the same IF. Next, the four IF signals (containing four BB channels each) are converted to four different sub-bands at RF. This requires four additional LO frequencies. In this way, the up-conversion of the 16 BB channels only requires eight LO signals. The RX can be realized as a down-conversion tree from D-band to BB, using the same LO scheme.

The careful design of the frequency plan makes it possible a further peculiarity of the proposed transceiver architecture. All LO frequencies are integer multiples of the same number: 2.16 GHz, which corresponds to the channel spacing (see Fig. 2). This allows one to generate all LO frequencies using integer- N frequency multiplication [14] from the same common input reference. That technique has been proven very effective in generating multiple LO signals with adjacent channels spurs smaller than -25 dBc [15], [16]. This feature is important since channel-to-channel interference should be kept below -20 dBc in order to enable a good enough signal to interference plus noise ratio (SINR) for high-order modulations such as 16-QAM or 64-QAM [16]. Phase noise (PN) is also a limiting factor for high-order modulations. The investigation of [16] indicates that the PN at 1 MHz offset from the carrier and the noise floor should be better than -98 dBc/Hz and -120 dBc/Hz, respectively, in order to degrade by less than 1.5 dB the SINR.

This paper presents an implementation of the above-described architecture. The proposed transmitter comprises a first TX_IF up-conversion and channel-aggregation stage and a second up-conversion and channel-aggregation stage of only the two upper frequency channels of the TX_RF shown in Fig. 2. Therefore, it brings 8 BB channels to 8 adjacent channels at D-band, occupying a band of 17.8 GHz around 149 GHz. This architecture can attain half the total data-rate with respect to the 16-channel architecture but, thanks to the modular design, it has the same energy efficiency and allows us to provide a first validation of the feasibility of the proposed technique.

B. Link Budget Analysis

The transmitter power (P_{TX}) values used in the calculations of Fig. 1 are the effective output power for modulated signal. The TX circuits should be able to provide significantly higher output power to take into account the peak-to-average ratio of the transmitted signals. A back-off of 10 dB is generally required for multi-channel 16-QAM, so that the 1-dB

TABLE I
LINK BUDGET ANALYSIS

Parameter	Per channel	Full band
BW (GHz)	2.16	IF: 2×4×2.16 RF 8×2.16
BB I or Q diff. peak amp. (mV @ 100 Ω)	750	
BB I or Q rms amp. (mV @ 100 Ω)	270	
BB to IF up-converter gain (dB)	-29	
IF signal power (dBm)	-30.4	-24.4 (×2)
D-band TX gain (dB)	37	
EIRP@1dBCP (dBm)	17.4	26.4
Back-off (dB)	10	
EIRP for IF power (dBm)	7.4	16.4
Path Loss @ 1 m (dB)	75.8	
Rx antenna gain (dBi)	31	
Rx NF (dB)	18	
Rx Signal @ antenna aperture (dBm)	-37.4	-28.4
Rx Noise @ antenna aperture (dBm)	-62	-53
SNR	24.6	
EVM for BER 10 ⁻² on 16-QAM (dB)	-15	
Margin for other RF impairments (dB)	9.6	

compression point (1dBCP) TX output power has to be 10 dB higher than the value shown in Fig. 1. Realistic D-band amplifiers in CMOS technologies [17] provide a power significantly lower than the 21 dBm required for a 100 Gb/s link at 200m (see Fig. 1). Since this work focuses on pure CMOS transmitters, the goal is to demonstrate shorter-range (1 m) point-to-point links. This range could be further extended by using external III-V power amplifiers, as in [18].

The link budget analysis for a TX-to-RX distance of 1 m is presented in Table I. The EIRP at 1dBP corresponds to the average value obtained for the TX module with the proposed TA, as it will be shown in Section IV and V. The RX is a commercial D-band down-converter equipped with a similar TA fed by a 10 dBi standard horn. The characterization of this antenna is also presented in Section IV. Average values have been used in the calculation per channel, since most parameters vary across the different channels, especially at D-band. The target raw bit error rate (BER) is 10⁻². It would result in an acceptable packet error rate (PER) of 10⁻⁴ with reasonable LDPC forward-error correction codes [19]. The required error vector magnitude (EVM) for a 16 QAM and BER = 10⁻² is -15 dB (18%). The EVM of the received symbols for each individual baseband channel is affected by signal-to-noise ratio and other impairments, such as phase noise, I/Q imbalance, non-linearity, and interferences coming from adjacent channels. The overall EVM can be calculated using the following equation:

$$EVM_{rms} = \sqrt{10^{-SNR/10} + \phi_{rms}^2 + other\ impairments}, \quad (1)$$

where the root mean square (rms) EVM, EVM_{rms} , is given by

$$EVM_{rms} = 10^{EVM/20}, \quad (2)$$

and ϕ_{rms} is the rms jitter in radians due to the phase noise of the LOs. It can be related to the time-domain rms jitter by:

$$\phi_{rms} = jitter_{rms} \cdot 2\pi f_c, \quad (3)$$

where $jitter_{rms}$ is the rms jitter in seconds, obtained from the integration of the phase noise of the LO over the signal BW, and f_c is the carrier frequency in Hz. If only the phase noise impairment is considered, in order to achieve an EVM_{rms} of 18% (-15 dB), the oscillators phase noise should introduce less than 160 fs of rms jitter at 140 GHz (considering a BB signal BW from 10 KHz to 1 GHz, and an SNR = 20.6 dB, as shown in Table I). This value is very constraining. When other RF impairments are considered, the jitter should be even smaller. In order to alleviate the constraints on the TX building blocks, some RF impairment compensation mechanisms are introduced in the digital BB receiver, such as carrier frequency-offset (CFO) and I/Q imbalance compensation, channel equalization and slow phase noise tracking and compensation. These techniques are briefly presented in Section III-C.

III. TRANSMITTER CHIP SET

The scheme of the proposed TX is shown in Fig. 3. The TX is composed of two different circuits. The first one implements the first up-conversion and channel-aggregation step of Fig. 2, and the second one implements the final up-conversion and channel aggregation at the D-band. Each circuit is assembled in a different module board. The D-band module board includes antennas-in-package (AiPs) that is described in the Section IV.

A. Frequency Generation

Both circuits integrate the multiple LO generators required for the up-conversion of the various channels. They are based on large integer frequency multiplications from a common input referenced. More details can be found in [14], [15].

The four LO signals required for the first up-conversion operation are shown in Fig. 4. The PN at 1 MHz offset is better than -100 dBc/Hz and the PN noise floor is better than -120 dBc/Hz. The LO signals for the second up-conversion step (the two highest LO frequencies) are shown in Fig. 5a. The PN at 1 MHz offset is also smaller than -100 dBc/Hz and the

Fig. 3. Block diagram of the transmitter, comprising two units of four BB-to-IF up-converters, and an IF-to-D-band TX IC, which excites the antenna feeds of the flat lens.

Fig. 4. LO signals spectrum and PN for the BB-IF up-converter (TX_IF).

PN noise floor is better than -125 dBc/Hz. Note that the input reference used in these measurements for the TX_RF circuit comes from a commercial 4.32-GHz PLL. This signal is multiplied by 19 and 21 to obtain the two required LO frequencies. The same reference signal frequency is further divided by two by a commercial frequency divider to feed the reference input of the TX_IF circuit. The latter one realizes frequency multiplication by integer numbers (27, 28, 29 and 30) to generate the four LO signals required for the BB-to-IF up-conversion. Fig. 5b shows the phase noise (PN) measured using single-tone signals at the output of the full BB-to-D-band TX, for the two extreme D-band channels, resulting from the combination of PN of the two LO signals of each up-conversion step. The 1 MHz offset PN is degraded compared to the isolated LO signals PN, because both LO signals combine coherently for generating the tone at the D-band, since they come from the same reference. The integrated jitter is also reported in the table in Fig. 5b, for two cases. The first column is the raw integrated jitter as obtained from the phase noise measurements. The second column is the effective jitter after applying the filtering of the digital phase tracking algorithm based on scattered pilots that operates up to 5 MHz frequency offset. Note that this phase tracking technique allows reducing the jitter to the required levels discussed in Section II. Additionally, LO spurs in the adjacent channel frequencies are smaller than -30 dBc in the worst case. All these features enable multi-channel operation with modulation schemes up to 64-QAM over individual channel BWs of 2.16 GHz.

B. Baseband-to-Intermediate Frequency Up-Converter

The BB-to-IF up-converter and channel-aggregation IC that implements the TX_IF (see Fig. 3) is composed of four similar lanes, each for a different I/Q differential BB input. They include a second order filter, an I/Q up-conversion mixer and an IF amplifier, as well as a dedicated LO generator each. The four LO frequencies are set to 58.32 GHz, 60.48 GHz, 62.64 GHz and 64.8 GHz, so that the four BB channels are up-

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. (a) LO signals spectra and phase noise for the D-band up-converter (TX_RF). (b) Overall phase noise and jitter for the combined LOs (TX_IF + TX-RF) for the two extreme D-band channels.

Fig. 6. BB-to-IF up-converter board and IC photograph (TX_IF).

Fig. 7. (a) Single-tone characterization of the BB-to-IF TX. The main responses for each BB channel input are shown in solid lines and the leakage to adjacent channels due to LO spurs in dashed lines. (b) Typical IF output spectrum for modulated BB inputs, when all BB inputs are on and (c) when only CH2 and CH4 BB inputs are on.

converted to adjacent IF channels, centered at 61.56 GHz. The outputs of the four lanes are combined using an on-chip passive 4-way hybrid. Its average insertion loss is 8 dB across the IF band, with a ± 1 dB variation. The IC is flip-chipped on a connectorized board, as shown in Fig. 6. The BB-to-IF IC is fabricated in 45-nm CMOS silicon-on-insulator (SOI) technology and occupies an area of 2×3.5 mm². Its power consumption is 450 mW from a 1 V supply.

The maximum gain from any of the BB inputs to the combined output is -26.5 dB. It includes a 1.5-dB loss due to the input BB connectors board traces, and a 4-dB loss on the IF output trace and connector. Each lane has 9 dB and 6 dB of programmable gain variation at the BB filters and IF amplifier, respectively. The 1-dB output compression point for the maximum gain is -22 dBm per channel. When all channels are combined, the total output power increases by 6 dB. The gain value is chosen to account for large dynamic ranges at the BB input (e.g. a few hundreds of mV) and a low enough IF power is chosen to avoid saturating the D-band transmitter.

One of the main limitations of channel-aggregation architectures is the channel-to-channel interferences. They are caused by two main mechanisms. First, the LO spurs at frequencies in adjacent channels produce some leakage from channel to channel. The spurs are due to the LO generator architecture that is based on frequency multiplication (see Section III-A). The measured LO leakage of the proposed transmitter is less than -30 dBc in every channel, as shown in Fig. 7a. Secondly, the Nyquist replicas of the BB signals may fall in adjacent channels. Fig. 7b shows the IF output spectrum for 1.8 Gbauds modulated BB signal inputs. The BB signals come from a multi-channel arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) using a sampling rate of 2.5 GS/s. Note that each BB signal (I and Q) has a BW of 900 MHz. The second order filter

of each lane reduces out-of-band Nyquist replicas, but does not completely eliminate them, as shown in Fig. 7c. The measured signal-to-interferer ratio (SIR) between the wanted channel and the replicas is 20 dB in the worst case, obtained by comparing Fig. 7b and Fig. 7c for CH1 and CH2. This SIR is high enough for a 16-QAM but unsuited for 64-QAM. The EVM of the other channels at the output of the BB-to-IF transceiver when baseband CH1 and CH3 are off is -20.7 dB for CH2 and -21.6 dB for CH4. When CH1 and CH3 are activated, the EVM for CH2 and CH4 is reduced to -16.9 dB and -19.8 dB, respectively. The EVM of CH2, that is affected by leakage from CH1 and CH3, is increased by 3.8 dB whereas the EVM of CH4, degraded by CH3 leakage, increases by 1.8 dB. This limitation can be overcome in future versions of the IC by further increasing the filter order.

The 16-QAM constellations shown in Fig. 8 are measured for the four BB channels contained in the IF signal at 61.56 GHz, by connecting a sampling oscilloscope to the IF output of the TX_IF up converter. The EVM varies between 10.2% to 14%, depending on the channel. The channel-to-channel interference is more relevant on CH2 and CH3, as they both have two neighboring channels. Each single BB channel at the input of the circuit conveys a 1.8 Gbaud signal generated using an 8-channel AWG (4 Is and 4 Qs) with 750 mV of peak-to-peak amplitude and a crest factor of 0.36. The total IF output power is -24.4 dBm.

C. D-band Multichannel Transmitter

The IF-to-D-band up-conversion and transmission is performed by a two-channel TX module similar to that proposed in [6]. Each of the two lanes is composed of an IF amplifier, an up-conversion mixer and a power amplifier (PA),

Fig. 8. IF output constellations for 16-QAM, 1.8 Gbauds BB inputs. The IF signal power is -24.4 dBm.

Fig. 9. D-band multi-channel TX microphotograph.

impinging at boresight and at 45° are greater than -0.2 dB and -1.2 dB, respectively, from 120 GHz to 160 GHz.

In both modules, the centers of LB and UB patch arrays are offset by 0.675 mm with respect to the x -axis. Thus, the H-plane (yz -plane) cuts of their radiation patterns are not maximum at boresight. The simulated patterns at 148 GHz of the stand-alone antennas of Fig. 11 are plotted in Fig. 13a. They reach maximum values at $\pm 18^\circ$, for LB and UB array, respectively. At the same frequency, the boresight realized gain is 7.5 dBi, i.e. 1.3 dB less than the peak value. The realized boresight gain varies less than 0.8 dB from 135 to 160 GHz (see Fig. 13b).

C. Transmitarray Design and Optimization

The same flat lens is used for the folded and the standard TA systems. The UCs of the lens are designed as asymmetric linear polarizers [20], [21], using only three metal layers, without any vias. The outer layers of all UCs are orthogonal wire grid polarizers. The element on the inner layer of each UC, referred to as rotator, is designed to rotate by 90° the incident field and introduce on it the desired phase shift. The stack-up of the lens comprises the same low-cost substrate materials of the AiPs and is shown in the insets of Fig. 10. The UC periodicity is $0.75 \text{ mm} \times 0.75 \text{ mm}$. Sixteen UCs were optimized using split rings and I-shaped patches (see inset of Fig. 10a). The simulated transmission coefficients of the UCs, under normal incidence and in an infinite array environment, are plotted in Fig. 14.

Fig. 11. (a) Exploded view and (b) stack-up of the AiP with the two 1×2 patch arrays used to radiate the LB and UB signals and illuminate the flat lens.

Fig. 12. (a) Bottom side of the AiP module with the flip-chipped TX IC and detail of UB and LB outputs and microstrip feeds of the antennas. Top side of the AiP for: (b) the standard TA and (c) the folded TA, including the RPSR.

Their amplitudes are all above -1 dB between 125 GHz and 160 GHz. In the same band, all phase responses are linear with frequency and provide an almost uniform 4-bit quantization of the 2π phase range.

A 48×48 TA excited by a 10-dBi standard gain horn was realized and characterized to validate the UC design and test a flat lens with an illumination law similar to that enforced by the AiP module. The focal distance between lens and horn is 25 mm. The lens phase profile was optimized at 140 GHz with the aid of an *ad-hoc* numerical tool [22]. It uses ray tracing, the simulated far field radiated by the feed and the scattering parameters of the UCs, to calculate the TA gain pattern. The measured gain frequency response and radiation patterns are in tight agreement with the computed values, as shown in Fig. 15.

The lens for the TX systems was designed to achieve a boresight gain higher than 25 dBi, using the aforementioned numerical tool. It comprises 48×48 UCs, corresponding to an electrical size of $17.8\lambda_0 \times 17.8\lambda_0$, where λ_0 is the free-space wavelength at 148 GHz. The focal distance for the standard TA was set at $F_0 = 25$ mm, which provides a good tradeoff among peak gain, BW and height of the antenna system. The spatial distribution of the UC phase shifts in the TA was optimized at

Fig. 13. (a) Realized gain patterns (yz -plane cuts) at 148 GHz and (b) boresight gain as function of frequency of the focal-plane antenna (see Fig. 2), when fed by either the LB or the UB input line.

Fig. 14. Simulated transmission coefficients of the 16 unit-cells of the TA, under normal incidence: (a) amplitude and (b) phase.

Fig. 15. (a) Measured and simulated peak gain of the broadside TA excited by a standard 10-dBi horn, at a distance of 25 mm, as functions of frequency. (b) Measured and simulated co-polarized gain patterns (xz -plane) at 140 GHz.

Fig. 16. (a) Phase compensation of the 48×48 TA designed for standard and folded modules at 148 GHz. (b) Computed realized gain of the standard TA.

Fig. 17. Pictures of the: (a) standard TA and (b) folded TA active module.

148 GHz, assuming that the phase center of the primary source is aligned to the lens center. It is presented in Fig. 16a. The realized gain patterns of the stand-alone antennas (see Fig. 11) were used in the TA design and to evaluate the antenna gain of the standard TA system. Similarly to the antenna feed, the H-plane patterns of the TA slightly tilt from boresight. The computed boresight gain of the standard TA system varies less than 1 dB from 138 GHz to 156 GHz (see Fig. 16b), with a peak of 27.2 dBi. The difference between maximum and boresight gain values at 148 GHz is 1.7 dB.

Two samples of the planar lens were assembled on the focal-plane antenna boards, using plastic spacers. Both antenna systems are shown in Fig. 17. The flat lens in the folded TA is rotated by 90° with respect to that in the standard TA. It is placed at a distance $F = 8.3$ mm from the feed. It is worth noting that, in the folded TA, the flat lens is in the Fresnel region of the source, whereas it is in far-field region in the standard TA.

V. ACTIVE ANTENNA SYSTEM CHARACTERIZATION

A. Measurement Setup

The two antenna systems were characterized in an anechoic chamber. Radiation patterns and EIRP were measured at the output 1-dB compression point of the TX IC. The antenna under test (AUT) was mounted on a two-axis positioner. The receiver, located at 3.1 m from the AUT, includes a 20-dBi D-band horn and a commercial down-converter (VDI-SAX). The measurement setup and the instruments driving the TX modules are shown in Fig. 18. As described in Section III-C, the TX IC on the focal-plane antenna module has two up-conversion lanes, which are excited, for simplicity, by the same V-band signal at the TX module IF input (IF IN, see Fig. 12a). When the IC is fed by a single-tone at IF IN, each up-conversion lane provides simultaneously a tone in the LB and in the UB at the corresponding IC output. The AUTs were tested by sweeping the frequency of the input tone (IF IN port), so that their performance at the corresponding tones in the LB and UB could be measured at the same time, using a spectrum analyzer

connected to the RX. The received power at the RX was measured as a function of frequency and elevation angle in the principal planes (xz - and yz -plane) of each AUT. The EIRP was evaluated from these experimental data by subtracting the RX gain and the path loss (~ 65 dB at 140 GHz).

B. Experimental Results and Discussion

The measured radiation patterns of the standard TA and folded TA, at the center frequencies of the LB (143.64 GHz) and UB (152.28 GHz), are plotted in Fig. 19 and Fig. 20, respectively. They were obtained for an IF input tone at 61.56 GHz. The patterns of each AUT are normalized to the maximum power received at 143.64 GHz. The output power of TX IC in the LB is, in average, 3 dB higher than in the UB. The difference between the measured received power values at the two frequencies is 3 dB for the standard TA, whereas it is 1.8 dB for the folded TA. This 1.2-dB spread does not seem to be due to the different TA architectures, but it is mainly attributed to the different power delivered to the antennas in the two modules. Indeed, the variability of the IC assembly process, e.g. the deformations of the C4 micro-bumps used for flip-chipping the IC, and fabrication tolerances, can affect the output impedance matching of the IC to the feeding lines of the antennas and result in sample-to-sample variations of the IC to AiP insertion losses. For typical radius and height variations of the solder bumps and considering the nominal AiP input impedance, the estimated IC to AiP insertion loss, obtained from full-wave parametric simulation, is 2 dB.

The radiation patterns of the folded TA are overall similar to those of the standard TA. However, their main beams are slightly narrower and higher side lobe levels (SLLs) are observed, especially for large elevation angles. These differences can be explained with near-field coupling effects between the source and the planar lens.

For both TA systems, the xz -plane cuts are maximum at boresight. The yz -plane patterns point toward negative angles in the LB, and toward positive angles in the UB, due to the off-focus position of the respective feeds. For both TAs, the angular distance of the peaks of the beams at 143.64 GHz and 152.28 GHz is 2°, and the power received at boresight is ~ 1.2 dB lower than the peak received power. This gain drop is consistent with the simulated gain of the primary source (see Fig. 13) and of the standard TA.

The measured boresight EIRP is plotted as a function of frequency in Fig. 21, for both systems, with and without flat lenses. The frequency behavior, including the dips around 148 GHz, is mostly determined by the D-band TX IC gain response and by its output matching. Indeed, the gain responses of the

Fig. 18. Experimental setup for the characterization of the active antenna system in an anechoic chamber.

feed modules and TA antennas are quite flat in this frequency range, as it can be seen in Fig. 13b and Fig. 16b. The EIRP of the AiP illuminating the standard TA is higher than that of the AiP for the folded TA in the LB (see Fig. 21a). This difference is due, in part, to the variability of the IC assembly process and related IC-to-AiP mismatch. Similar differences are observed between the EIRP of the full antenna systems (see Fig. 21b). Overall, the EIRP of the folded TA module is close to that of the standard TA, in terms of BW and absolute values.

The peak EIRP for both systems is about 30 dBm. The over-the-air aggregation of LB and UB signals greatly enhances the EIRP with respect to similar modules limited by the losses of guided power-combining components (~ 10 dB in [9]). In conclusion, the folded TA enables a three-fold reduction of the

Fig. 19. Measured co-polarization patterns of the standard TA module at the center frequencies of the LB and UB: (a) xz -plane cut; (b) yz -plane cut.

Fig. 20. Measured co-polarization patterns of the folded TA module at the center frequencies of the LB and UB: (a) xz -plane cut; (b) yz -plane cut.

Fig. 21. Measured EIRP at boresight ($\theta = 0^\circ$): (a) AiP modules without lens and (b) full TA systems (standard and folded TA) over the LB and UB.

antenna height, paving the way for a monolithic integration of AiP and flat lens, without significantly degrading the system performance.

C. Antenna Gain Estimation

The realized gain values of both antenna systems have been retrieved using the measured EIRP values and an estimation of the power delivered by the D-band TX IC to the antennas. This power has been determined from measurements performed on a similar AiP module, presented in [9, Fig. 13], which comprises the same D-band TX IC. This test board includes input microstrip lines for the V-band IF IN and the REF IN signals, and a substrate integrated waveguide (SIW) diplexer that combines the two output signals of the D-band TX IC. A vertical microstrip-to-waveguide transition at the output of the diplexer enables the interconnection of the board to a 20-dBi standard-gain horn antenna. The EIRP of the test board with the horn has been characterized in the anechoic chamber, with the same measurement setup and procedure used for the TA systems. Next, the output power of the D-band TX IC on this board has been evaluated subtracting the gain of the horn and adding the insertion losses of the transition and of the diplexer, obtained from measurements on stand-alone versions of these components. It is worth nothing that this method neglects possible impedance mismatches at the outputs of the IC, thus overestimating the available output power.

Eventually, the realized gain of standard and folded TA systems has been evaluated dividing the measured EIRP by the estimated output power of the IC at the input of the AiP, in the LB and UB. The results are plotted in Fig. 22. Note that they include the IC-to-AiP mismatch loss. The average realized gains of the standard and folded TA are about 26.5 dBi and 26 dBi, respectively, corresponding to aperture efficiencies of 11.6% and 10.3% at 146 GHz. These values are very close to the simulated realized gain of the standard TA in Fig. 16b.

VI. WIRELESS LINK CHARACTERIZATION

The circuits and modules described in the previous sections are inserted in a hardware-in-the-loop (HiL) validation platform that allows one to implement a full wireless link from a multichannel digital BB TX to a multichannel digital BB RX.

A. Experimental Set-up

The block diagram of the HiL platform is illustrated in Fig. 23. At the TX side, a multichannel arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) provides differential I and Q BB signals to the BB-to-IF up-converter module. A single 4-channel module

Fig. 22. Estimated realized antenna gain at boresight of the standard (dashed line) and folded TA (solid line), in the LB and UB.

is used since the D-band TX prototype re-uses the same IF input port for the two up-conversion lanes, resulting in 8 channels at RF with just 4 channels at IF. The input reference for the two up-converters are generated using the same commercial PLL. For the D-band TX, a 4.32 GHz signal directly provided by the PLL is used. A second output of the PLL is connected to a commercial frequency divider that delivers the 2.16 GHz signal required by the BB-to-IF up-converter. At the RX side, a commercial D-band down-converter module is used (VDI SAX). It features an average conversion gain of 4 dB and a noise figure (NF) around 18 dB. It brings the D-band signal to an IF band spanning from DC to 18 GHz. A dedicated LO signal of 26.19 GHz that is internally multiplied by a factor of 6 is used to down-convert the received signal at D-band. The IF output of the VDI SAX RX is sent to a 200 MS/s digital sampling scope (DSO). Both the AWG and the DSO are controlled by a Matlab code that implements the digital BB (DBB) TX and RX by generating the waveforms sent by the AWG and processing the waveform sampled by the DSO. The PLL used for the TX IC and the LO of the RX module are not synchronized and are provided by independent signal sources.

B. Digital Baseband

The baseband signals are composed of three preamble sections and a series of payload symbols, each one composed of several repetitions of the same block (see Fig. 24). The three preambles are used for carrier frequency offset (CFO), I/Q mismatch and channel estimation in the RX, respectively. The payload section includes scattered binary phase-shift keying (BPSK) modulated pilots that are used for phase tracking in the DBB RX. The preambles use Zadoff-Chu sequences (different for each BB channel). The payload is modulated using single carrier (SC) schemes since at D-band frequencies, the channel is very close to line-of-sight and more complex modulation schemes such as OFDM would not provide any benefit. Furthermore, SC modulation has a good resistance to phase rotations. Frequency Domain Equalization (FDE) is used to

mitigate inter-symbol interference. The symbol rate is set to 1.8 Gbauds, enabling reasonable up-sampling and down-sampling ratios from the AWG available sampling frequencies (limited to 2.5 GS/s in our case). The DBB TX is implemented with a sequence of digital operation shown in Fig. 24. The symbols are shaped using a root raised cosine (RCC) filter with parameter 0.17. Fig. 24 includes an example of I and Q waveforms with the set of parameter values indicated in the same figure. The preambles length values are optimized after system level simulations as a tradeoff between payload overhead and parameters estimation accuracy. The cyclic prefix (CP) length of 32 samples (equivalent to 20 ns delay time) is long enough to account for the measured indoor channel delay spread obtained from channel sounding at D-band [23] for link distances up to 10 m.

On the RX DBB side, the signal waveform sampled by the DSO is first down converted numerically to BB and then separated into the individual BB channels. For each channel, the signal processing operations illustrated in Fig. 25 are applied in order to estimate the various RF impairments, apply correction algorithms and finally demodulate the payload symbols. The same RCC filter used in the DBB TX is implemented at the input of the DBB RX preceded by up-sampling and followed by down-sampling operations to bring the digital symbol rate from the scope ADC sampling rate to the DBB symbol rate of 1.8 Gbauds. Next, the synchronization preamble is compensated for I/Q mismatch using the estimation from the previous received frame. This is required for improving the synchronization accuracy. Then, an autocorrelation operation over the first preamble is used to find the optimal synchronization sample. The same preamble allows one to extract an estimation of the CFO from the phase drift along its various repetitions N_S compared to the expected phase

Fig. 23. Hardware-in-the-loop link validation platform: block diagram.

Fig. 24. Signal waveform and digital baseband TX block diagram.

Fig. 25. Digital baseband RX block diagram.

slope. If the estimated CFO is higher than a predefined threshold, the I/Q mismatch is estimated in the time domain using the second preamble. Otherwise, it can be estimated in the frequency domain after the FFT operation. In both cases, the CFO is corrected before performing the FFT. The channel is estimated using the third preamble in the frequency domain after the FFT and the correction is applied just before the inverse FFT operation. Finally, the residual phase wandering is estimated using the scattered pilots and corrected on the payload symbols in time domain, before proceeding to the demodulation and forward error correction decoding (channel decoding).

C. Measurements Results

The TX modules presented in Section III were mounted on plastic carriers and inserted in the HiL platform described in the previous sub-section in order to implement a full BB-to-BB link, as shown in Fig. 26. Each of the four BB I and Q differential input signals is generated using a sampling frequency of 2.5 GS/s. The baud rate is 1.8 Gbauds and 16-QAM is applied to the payload in each of the BB channels. The IF and D-band modules were connected using V-band connectors and a waveguide to minimize the losses. The link distance can be varied from a few tens of cm up to 1 m. For longer distances, as shown in what follows, the BER of the received 16-QAM signals drops below 10^{-2} .

The RX is implemented using the SAX down-converter described in the previous sub-section. The antenna is a TA of the same type of the TX antenna but optimized to be illuminated by a 10-dBi horn antenna. Its gain has been experimentally characterized (see Fig. 15, about 31 dBi). The received signal obtained at the IF output of the SAX down-converter is sampled using the DSO at 50 GS/s and, next, it is read and processed by the RX DBB. The AWG, controlled by the TX DBB, continuously generates a train of frames of 18 μ s of duration and spaced by 2 μ s, at each BB output. The scope triggers on the rising section of the frames preamble received at the RX and sends the data to the Matlab DBB RX that performs off-line demodulation and parameters extractions (e.g. signal power, EVM, BER, residual I/Q and CFO mismatch).

The two TA designs (standard and folded) provide similar EIRP levels, so that the link level results do not significantly vary when using one or the other. The results of Fig. 27 are obtained for a distance of 50 cm between the TX and the RX. Next, the link distance is varied between 0.15 m and 1.35 m. The HiL platform records the main performances of the latest 20 received frames and plots them, in a cyclic way, as shown in Fig. 28. Note that the link distance is not varied following a particular order. The dashed line indicates the current run. The received power (at the output of the SAX down-converter RX) varies from -24 dBm to -35 dBm across the full distance range considered. The overall BER varies from $2.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to $1.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$, and is smaller than 10^{-2} for distances below 1 m. The EVM varies from channel to channel, since not all channels are received with the same power and some of the RF impairments, such as channel-to-channel interference, do not affect all channels in the same way. The individual channel EVM

recorded for different link distances are plotted in Fig. 29a, as functions of power received per channel. Two factors contribute to the power and EVM spread across the channels. The first one is the frequency variation of the EIRP, shown in Fig. 21. The second one is the variation of the NF and RX gain of the SAX down-converter with the input frequency as shown in Fig. 29b. The EIRP variation across a single channel is compensated by the channel equalization performed in the digital receiver for each channel. Channel-to-channel differences on the average EIRP for each channel, along with variations of the average NF, result in different SNR values for each channel and, therefore, different EVMs and different error rates. Some of this spread is compensated by adjusting the baseband channels power, but this mechanism is limited to a few dB of compensation, so that still some residual spread is observed in the signal arriving at the DSO. Nevertheless, compared to the results presented in [8], the link distance is increased by a factor 2.4, reaching 1 m.

Fig. 26. Point-to-point link demonstration at a distance of 1 m.

Fig. 27. (a) RX signal spectrum and (b) 16-QAM constellation for a 50-cm link.

Fig. 28. (a) RX signal power and (b) BER for various link distances.

Fig. 29 (a) EVM as a function of RX power per channel, for several link distances. (b) Gain and NF of the SAX receiver down converter.

Point-to-point communications with 8 channels using 16-QAM is demonstrated, providing a total rate of 57.6 Gb/s with a DC power consumption of 1.58 W, resulting in an energy efficiency of 27.4 pJ/bit.

VII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The presented TX is compared, in terms of design and performance, with state-of-the-art D-band transmitters and links in Table 2. In [3], an interesting combination of CMOS TX with external InP PAs is proposed to increase the output power. Its energy efficiency is comparable to that achieved in this work, but the system in [3] operates over a narrower band (6 GHz). The phased array modules reported in [4] and [5] also achieve a relatively narrowband performance and their energy consumption is significantly larger. The TX proposed in this work attains the largest data-rate among state-of-the-art D-band

modules, as well as the lowest TX energy efficiency (27.4 pJ/b) including the LO generation, conversely to [3] that uses an external mmW LO-generation system, whose power consumption is not reported. The performance demonstrated in this work is enabled by the high-gain and low-cost flat lens antenna system and by the wideband, energy-efficient channel-aggregation architecture. A 1-m link has been demonstrated and characterized using a 25-dBi gain TA at the TX and a 31-dBi TA at the RX. A data rate of 57.6 Gb/s has been achieved with a multichannel 16-QAM scheme, providing a BER better than 10^{-2} . Furthermore, the proposed channel-aggregation architecture enables dynamically adaptable transceivers, because some lanes can be switched off, including the digital signal processing and interfaces, if the peak data-rate is not required. This solution allows one to adapt the power consumption to the required data-rate and achieve a nearly constant energy efficiency, as opposed to the other full-band, single-channel architectures [2]-[5] that will consume always as if using the peak data-rate.

Finally, the proposed D-band antenna system has been optimized to reduce the distance between the high-gain flat lens and the active feeding module, using a folded TA architecture. The latter enables a three-fold reduction of the focal distance, compared to a standard TA. It has been shown that this low-profile antenna design does not degrade the performance of the proposed TX system in its 11.7% operating BW. The main drawback of the proposed approach is that fixed-beam TAs do not enable beam self-alignment. This limitation can be overcome by using electronically reconfigurable flat lenses, such as the one reported in [24].

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Table 2. Performance comparison of recent D-band transmitters integrated with antenna systems.

Reference	[3]	[4]	[5]	This Work
Package Technology	LTCC Interposer	Radio on PCB	Radio on PCB	Radio on PCB
ICs Technology	22nm FDSOI + 0.25 InP HBT	130nm SiGe BiCMOS	45nm RFSOI	45nm RFSOI
TX architecture	Single channel BB to D-band direct conversion External LO@15 GHz	2x2 Channels RF beamformer	2x4 RF Front-end + IF Beamformer External LO@22 GHz	BB-to-IF multi-channel up-converter + channel aggregation RF Front-end with integrated LO generation
Antenna system and gain (if available)	Antenna on LTCC (8 linear patch arrays) 12 dBi	Antenna on Glass (2x2 patch array)	Antenna on with on-chip feed (2x4 patch array)	Patch antennas on PCB + Flat lens (PCB) ~25 dBi
Frequency (GHz)	131-137	130-150,150-165	136-147	140-158
EIRP@1dBBCP*/Psat** (dBm)	27.5**	18**	17.5*	26.4*
#Channels x Ch. BW (GHz)	1 x 6	1 x 6	1 x 3	8 x 2.16
Tx Pdc (mW)	760	1060	1848	1580
Peak DR (Gb/s)/Modulation	30 (64-QAM)	30 (64-QAM)	10.5 (64-QAM)	57.6 (16-QAM)
EIRP @ Peak DR (dBm)	21	8	10.5	16.4
Link distance (cm)	15	NA	65	100
TX energy efficiency (pJ/bit)	25.4	35.3	176	27.4

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processing. His interest included Ultra-Wide Band systems, digital compensation of RF imperfections, antenna beamforming. Since 2006, he has been involved in the development of various millimeter-wave systems in CMOS or BiCMOS technologies, including 79-GHz Short-Range Radars, 60-GHz Wireless HD and WiGig. In 2011, he led CEA-Leti millimeter-wave designs and began the development of systems for 5G small cells, promoting the use of mmw bands for 5G, and towards short-range chip-to-chip communications and contactless connectors. Lately, he has been studying and developing architectures for channel aggregation in D-band, targeting >100Gbps wireless communications.

Mr. Dehos has been involved in many collaborative projects funded by European Commission, as well as in many industrial bilateral projects with transfer of technology. He is also active in the promotion of mmw wireless technologies for particle physics.